

An Agile Methodology Approach on the Automation of the Recruitment Processing of Company XYZ

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ABSTRACT

Company XYZ is a medical transcription healthcare company that is facing problems in handling their current online recruitment process for its applicants. Their recruitment process makes use of only their email to gather data given by the applicants, and Microsoft Excel to save the given data. With this, they experienced the following issues: (1) time-inefficiency when it comes to gathering information, (2) overlooked application emails; and (3) no accountability trackers for its employees. The researchers thought of a solution by creating an online recruitment web application, where the applicants and HR department can interact with each other without having the need to go through emails individually. Furthermore, the web application displays which HR account made changes on a specific applicant that is registered in the database. Through the usage of an agile methodology, the researchers were able to adapt to the requests and changes given by the Company, thus making the system up to date, relevant, and accurate based on the needs of the Company.

KEYWORDS

Online Recruitment, Agile, Human Resource, Medical Transcription, Job Application

1 INTRODUCTION

Company XYZ is a medical transcription company that interprets and transcribes medical information from doctors and physicians to patients and clients. Throughout the meetings the researchers had with the client, the Company has mentioned that their process of recruiting new medical transcriptionists was through email. As this is a manual process that the HR department accomplishes, two issues arise, namely human and technical error. Technical error can arise

when the email that is sent by the applicant goes to the spam portion of the email and is overlooked by the HRM employee. It is one of the major issues encountered by the HR department as overlooked applicants count as a missed opportunity in employing a potential medical transcriptionist. Another issue arises when the HRM employee manually transfers data of the applicant to an Excel sheet. This is where human error could occur. Especially during the transferring of information as typographical errors are possible. On top of this, communication with the applicant can be quite difficult if there are errors made during the tabulation of data. Also, currently, there is no way of tracking or tracing which employee last logged into the email, as the HRM only logs into one email account. This can also lead to problems. According to the company, if the applicant has any concerns or questions they would need to find out who was the last HRM employee who communicated with the applicant. This leads to time wasted, because instead of processing the applicants, they would need to find the employee.

After identifying the different issues encountered by the Company, the researchers aim to (1) minimize errors made during the encoding process of applicant information, (2) make the communication between the applicant and HR faster and efficient, (3) add accountability trackers for HR employees; and (4) lastly, prevent instances wherein applications are overlooked.

The research also makes use of feedback forms and the Likert scale [5] in order to gauge whether or not the system is in compliance with the requirements of the client and the company. The result of the feedback forms at the end of the research had been given a positive score by the Senior HR Manager.

2 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Most traditional recruiting processes can be split into three stages: (1) Setting up detailed employment standards and job description for each job listing. (2) Verification of application forms and resumes. (3) Performance tests and other evaluation aids [4]. While these stages are important for any job recruitment, it still takes time especially when performed in an archipelago like the Philippines which has 7100 islands. With that said, given the competitive environment, the traditional recruitment process may prove to be ineffective [6]. Still, this problem could be easily addressed by using mediums that would utilize remote means of communication, in this case, an online recruitment system. The usage of an online recruitment system removes unnecessary paperwork, introduces streamlined workflow systems, reliable database applications and efficient communication between applicants and managers, all of which are possible at a relatively low cost [1]. Online recruitment is a method used by applicants to apply for an advertised position by passing their resumes electronically to the website of the company that advertised the job offering, which is then stored in a database. This implies that anyone from anywhere can apply for an advertised job [2]. According to Mary Grace Ventura & Rex Bringula,

to have an efficient online recruitment system it must focus on: performance, reliability, security, and cost-effectiveness [1].

Performance refers to the capacity of the system to generate a list of applicants suitable for the job in a quick manner [1].

Reliability pertains to what extent the system can be expected to perform in its intended function. The system should produce required results, thus filtering out applicant forms without issues [1].

Security is the protection of the system towards unauthorized users. The system should have the mechanism to protect and control data provided by its users [1].

Cost-effectiveness refers to the justification of the amount of money spent on an investment that is comparable in an efficient manner [1].

3 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The following lays out the objectives of the research:

- to minimize errors that can occur during encoding of applicant information into the system
- to make communication with the applicant faster and more efficient
- to track the accountability of the employees when using the system
- to prevent the applicant from being overlooked

4 METHODOLOGY

This portion of the paper enumerates in detail the process that the researchers have undergone in order to actualize the online recruitment portal.

4.1 Research Design

The researchers used an Agile methodology based approach. This is because the researchers want to find out the most optimal and appropriate solutions to the problems that the Company faces. The researchers would keep in contact with the client and hold meetings in order for us to fully understand and grasp their business process. The researchers also asked them who the users of the system would be and have identified three key roles, the admin, the HRM, and the applicant. The tasks were completed in sprints. Each sprint would last 3-4 months. Reason being is that there were inefficiencies during the creation of the system.

4.2 Research Participants

The researchers interviewed the Senior HR Manager of Company XYZ, who is in charge of the recruitment process of the Company.

4.3 Data Gathering

As the research was completed during the coronavirus pandemic, the researchers are not allowed to visit the Company premises due to healthcare measures. Therefore all communications between the researchers and the Company is through email, Skype, or Google meet. Meetings with the Company are held quarterly. This is to gather necessary updated information needed by the researchers throughout the creation of the application.

Scrum meetings are done weekly and the schedule is subject to change depending on the availability of the researchers. The scrum meetings are held and last around 2-3 hours long. The purpose of these meetings is to ensure that there is progress being made on the system. The duration of the scrum meetings depends on the topics involved in the meeting. This is to ensure that the designated tickets to each researcher are done efficiently. Scrum meetings are used to update what has been done and what are the action plans needed until the next scrum meeting. It is also in the scrum meetings wherein the bottlenecks in the current recruitment process are identified and given solutions to as well.

4.4 Treatment of Data

The recruitment process of the Company was the primary data gathered by the researchers. As the different business processes were laid out, the researchers were able to carefully design the system based on the given data. With this, the researchers managed to identify the functional and non-functional requirements needed to build the system.

The recruitment process is a linear process that covers stages. Each recruitment stage has its own way of interaction between the HRM, applicant, and the application.

At the end of each sprint, stages that are done with its development are presented to the Company. This is to ensure that each stage has its proper functions and to update each stage if there are any changes in the process. Towards the end of each and every system demonstration, a feedback form is sent to the Company to assess the state of the system so that the researchers will know which parts need improving. The feedback form also serves as a meter on how satisfied the Company is with each system iteration demonstrated every meeting.

Since there are only two instances where the Company has filled-out the feedback form. The researchers had computed the average of each section, and overall average of the feedback rate. The average of each section indicates if that specific section is acceptable or not. An average that is lower than 3.50 is considered unacceptable and needs to be improved. A 3.50 average and above is acceptable. If the overall average is below 4.00, it is also considered unacceptable. If the system is unacceptable, improvements and changes will be made by the researchers.

4.5 Validation

The researchers created a prototype that addresses the Company's main problems in their recruitment process. These problems are, manual entry of applicant's details into Excel, email monitoring for each applicant, tracking of who last interacted with an applicant, and communication between the HRM and the applicant. Every end of sprint meetings with the Company, the researchers focus on the efficiency of each stage done. Towards the last two sprints, after the meeting, the Company is given a feedback form. The feedback form mainly contains the criteria: (1) Functional Stability, (2) Performance Efficiency, (3) Compatibility, (4) Usability, (5) Reliability, (6) Security, (7) Portability. The contents of the feedback form are based on ISO 25010 [3] focusing more on the needs of the application. The feedback form was given on a later date. The reason behind this is that the researchers focused more on improving the application towards the end of the project.

Each criteria covers parts of the research objectives. If Reliability, Usability, and Performance Efficiency scored neutral or lower, this means that errors can still occur during the transportation between the system to its database and vice versa. If Functional Stability, Portability, Reliability, and Performance Efficiency are deemed unacceptable, then the researchers need to improve the communicating with the applicant faster and more efficiently. If Security and Functional Stability are acceptable, this means that the application can track the accountability of the employees. If Compatibility and Reliability are acceptable, prevention of overlooking applicants is possible in the application.

5 FINDINGS

Based on the meetings with the client, the researchers were able to find out that Company XYZ conducts their recruitment via email. With that said, this process is prone to a multitude of problems. As previously mentioned, two problems can arise, specifically, human error and technical error. The company mentioned that there have been instances wherein time has been wasted because of the inefficiencies of the current process. An example of this is when the HR employees manually transfer the applicant information to the Excel spreadsheet. Not only does this waste time, but typographical errors could occur as well. The Company also has mentioned several other issues that they have encountered.

In order to combat these, the researchers have come up with the following software features and capabilities that have been tailored to address each of the issues. The features were then divided into three sprints so the work would be more manageable for the researchers.

Table 1: Problems with Corresponding Software Features

Problems	Software Features
Applicants get overlooked	-the system is able to automatically place the new applicants at the top of the list -the system is able to reflect real-time change into the system -system is able to search the applicant name using the search button
Typographical errors	-the system allows the applicants to edit their own details anytime -system must be able to keep the applicant's information up to date
Lack of accountability	-the system is able to automatically track which employee last interacted with the applicant
Communication problems	-the system allows communication the applicant and the HRM to communicate in -the system is able send email to applicant via SMTP

6 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Total number of sprints was three. Every sprint meeting, we give the Company a system demonstration on the accomplished stages of the recruitment process. While the demonstration is happening, the researchers and the Company discuss the improvements and updates for each stage. This is done in order to fulfill the function needed by the Company.

Table 2: Company Remarks

Sprint Number	Company Suggestions
Sprint 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Conditions of each recruitment stage ● Update the UI with Company colors ● Details needed from the HRM to the applicant during the training stage and the applicant needs to confirm the training. ● Newest applicant should be the first name on the table.
Sprint 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Add Company logo to the application

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Fix UI when it comes to the tables ● Change the employed stage page welcome text ● Add searching functions for the applicant list ● Remove footer from the application ● Change UI color of the table ● Change the user's name into all capital letters ● One button for all documents per applicant in the HRM side
<p>Sprint 3</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Remove reference table for changing the status of the applicant ● Add more status options to the applicant ● Change UI when changing password. Change “Password” into “New Password” ● Change UI when account is disabled. ● Change “IT” into “HRM”

With the Agile Methodology, the researchers were able to get an up-to-date recruitment process during the pandemic. Live feedback from the Company is also available while giving the system demonstration and guided access.

Through-out the after sprint meetings with the Company, additional functions and changes on the web pages that the applicant sees. Messages and information shown on the applicant’s web pages, is a part of communication to the applicant. Therefore, the applicant is aware of what stage of the recruitment process they are in and what is their status. Adding a search button to filter out applicants would prevent the older applications from being seen by the HR department.

When it comes to the feedback form, this was given out when the application already had complete UI and UX elements (Sprint 2). This feedback form helped the researchers navigate through important attributes of the system.

Table 3: System Average Score per Criteria of Client Feedback from Sprints 2 to 3

Criteria	Average Score (out of 5)
Functional Stability	4.17
Performance Efficiency	3.5
Compatibility	4.5
Usability	4
Reliability	3.75
Security	4.13
Portability	4.5
Overall Average Score of the System	4.08

7 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Adapting an Agile methodology, the researchers were able to identify the issues that the current recruitment process the company uses, as well as provide solutions to each problem. As a consequence, the researchers were able to adapt to a fast-paced working environment and were able to quickly get feedback from the client, making request changes as seamless as possible. Through weekly scrum meetings, the researchers were able to maintain a steady workflow, thus assuring the quality of work after every meeting. Throughout the development process, the researchers came to a realization that Agile methodology is best utilized with a small group of people that is constantly communicating to be able to overcome the issues that the team may encounter and to swiftly adapt accordingly.

The researchers also strongly believe that the system is able to address all of the problems that the Company faced. Problems such as applicants getting overlooked, typographical errors, lack of employee accountability, and communication problems. The system is able to adequately address all of the aforementioned problems that the Company has faced. The bottlenecks experienced by the Company and employees would be significantly reduced. This was all done through the agile methodology with open collaboration and communication with the Company that were able to meet all of their requirements and specifications.

The researchers recommend meeting the clients physically at least one time to completely immerse themselves once the sprints actually start. Also, the researchers recommend that after every application demonstration, a feedback form is prepared and given to the participants so

that essential data will be collected. Lastly, before the sprint starts, the researchers recommend to prepare one's self to fully commit to the weekly scrum meetings so that each team member has a grasp of the situation of the amount of progress done within the week.

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